

Synthesis of some Novel Boron-Schiff Base and Allied Derivatives[†]

J. P. TANDON

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004

Synthesis of some novel boron Schiff base and allied derivatives is described. These have been prepared by the different molar reactions of trialkoxy or phenoxyboranes, oxybis(diacetoxy borane), 2-isopropoxybenzo-1,3-dioxo-2-borole, 2-isopropoxy-1,3-dithia-2-borole, 2-isopropoxy-1,3-thiaza-2-borole, phenylboronic acid, boron trifluoride diacetic acid and boron trifluoride etherate with ligands of stereochemical as well as biological significance, viz. Schiff bases; azines, semi- and thio-semicarbazones and *S*-methyl or benzyldithiocarbazates. The mode of bonding in the resulting complexes has been deduced on the basis of uv, ir, mass and multinuclear resonance (¹H, ¹³C, ¹¹B, ¹⁹F) studies and some of these have been examined for their biocidal activity.

THE boron-nitrogen chemistry has been the focal point of attraction for the chemists during the last two decades and a large number of complexes having B-N bonds have been synthesised on account of their applications in diverse fields such as industry^{1,2}, agriculture^{3,4} and medicine^{5,6}. Probably due to the isoelectronic and isosteric nature of B-N and C-C bonds, the B-N chemistry is very extensive and diverse.

The chemistry of Schiff base complexes has attracted a great deal of attention ever since Pfeiffer carried out his pioneering research in 1930's. Schiff base complexes have subsequently been found to play an essential role in many biological processes, viz. transamination, decarboxylation, condensation, β -elimination and racemisation which are known to involve Schiff base intermediates. These find applications as algacides and plant growth regulators⁷ and their pharmacological applications as anticancer, antituberculostatic and antiinflammation agents as well as their uses as antiviral, antibiotic⁸ and anaesthetic agents⁹ have been described.

A variety of boron-Schiff base and allied derivatives can be synthesised by using trialkoxy- or phenoxyboranes, oxybis(diacetoxyboranes), 2-isopropoxybenzo-1,3-dioxo-2-borole, 2-isopropoxy-1,3-dithia-2-borole, 2-isopropoxy-1,3-thiaza-2-borole, phenyl boronic acid, boron trifluoride diacetic acid and boron trifluoride etherate as the starting materials.

Synthesis of boron derivatives involving alkoxy boranes :

In trialkoxyboranes, the electrophilic character of boron atom is reduced due to the back coordi-

nation from oxygen to boron (+M effect) and accordingly these behave as weak Lewis acids.

However, the aryloxyboranes behave as good Lewis acids due to -M effect and these form only the addition compounds.

The reactions of triisopropoxyborane with the Schiff bases derived by the condensation of β -diketones with alkyl or arylamines and hydroxyalkyl or arylamines are quite slow, whereas similar reactions with triethoxyborane are fast enough as well as straightforward. This is due to the fact that the covalent character increases with the greater +I effect of the alkyl group.

The reactions of triethoxyborane with *o*-hydroxy acetophenonealkyl or arylamines ($\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CCH}_3 : \text{NR}'$) in 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 molar ratios¹⁰ can be represented by the following general equation,

where, $n=1, 2$ or 3 ; $\text{R}' = \text{CH}_3, \text{C}_2\text{H}_5, n\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7, n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9, \text{C}_6\text{H}_5, o\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4, m\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4, p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4, \text{ClC}_6\text{H}_4$.

[†]Acharya J. C. Ghosh Memorial Lecture (1982) delivered under the auspices of the Indian Chemical Society on November 5, 1985 at Raipur.

The resulting derivatives can be structurally represented as

The diethoxymono-Schiff base and monoethoxyboron-bis-Schiff base derivatives undergo alcohol interchange reactions in presence of excess of tertiary butanol and these show the labile nature of ethoxy groups present in these derivatives.

However, reactions of triethoxyborane with bifunctional tridentate Schiff bases¹¹, such as 4-(hydroxy alkyl or aryl)amino-3-pentene-2-one, 3-(hydroxy alkyl or aryl)amino-1-phenyl-2-butene-1-one and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone hydroxyalkylimines take place in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios only.

where, $R = CH_3$ and C_6H_5 ; $X' = CH_2CH_2$, $CH(CH_2)_2CH_2$, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$, $CH(CH_2CH_2)_2$ and C_6H_4 .

The reactions of Schiff bases derived from 2,4-pentanedione are quite slow, whereas similar reactions with the Schiff bases of 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione are comparatively faster due to the $-I$ effect of the phenyl ring.

The 2 : 3 molar reactions of these Schiff bases with triethoxyborane simply result in the formation of a mixture of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 derivatives. The former can be separated from the resulting mixture by crystallising out from benzene-*n*-hexane (5 : 3) mixture. The non-formation of 2 : 3 derivatives can possibly be attributed to the steric factors as

the two boron atoms cannot accommodate the third ligand moiety in between.

where, HONOH = donor set of the bifunctional tridentate Schiff base.

However, the reaction of ethoxy boron mono Schiff base derivative with 1,4-dihydroxybenzene in 2 : 1 molar ratio proceeds as follows,

The formation of such a derivative can be explained on the basis of the smaller size of 1,4-dihydroxybenzene as compared to the Schiff base molecule.

Similar reactions of triethoxyborane with ligands having ONO and ONS donor systems, *i.e.* semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones¹² take place in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios.

where $X = O$ or S ; $Y = NH_2$.

The reactions of triethoxyborane with the Schiff bases derived by the condensation of *S*-methylthiocarbamate or *S*-benzylthiocarbamate (SMTZH₂) with salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, *o*-hydroxyacetophenone, 2,4-pentanedione or 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione¹³ can be represented by the following general equations,

In the ^1H nmr spectrum of 1:1 boron derivative, the disappearance of NH (δ 10.75) and SH (4.45) proton signals shows chelation of boron through oxygen and sulphur atoms, whereas in 1:2 derivative, these proton signals appear at δ 10.52 and 4.26 due to the existence of the resonating NH or SH proton of one of the ligand moiety. Further, two sets of proton signals are observed for every proton in 1:2 derivative with one set remaining at almost the same position as in the ligand itself. This clearly shows that one of the ligand moieties acts as a tridentate and another one as unidentate species.

The condensation of aromatic aldehydes or β -diketones with 2-aminoethanethiol, 2-aminopropanethiol or *o*-aminobenzenethiol results in the formation of cyclic products containing a thiazoline ring^{14,15}. However, in presence of metallic or non-metallic ions, isomerisation of these ligands to their tautomeric Schiff base form takes place^{16,17}.

The triisopropoxyborane undergoes facile reactions with benzothiazolines¹⁸ in 1:1 and 1:2 molar ratios and the resulting products can be structurally represented as

where, HO-N-SH = donor set of the ligand molecule.

In the ligands, the absence of ν_{SH} in the region 2660-2550 cm^{-1} and the appearance of a strong and sharp ν_{NH} band in the region 3350-3250 cm^{-1} are indicative of their benzothiazoline form in the solid state. However, the disappearance of ν_{NH} band as well as the absence of ν_{SH} band in the ir spectra of 1:1 boron complexes show the chelation of sulphur as well as nitrogen of the ligand moieties to the central boron atom. Further, in the case of boron complexes, a strong band around 1610 cm^{-1} is observed and this is due to the coordinated azomethine group.

The ligands derived by the condensation of *o*-mercaptoaniline with 2,4-pentanedione ($\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2$), salicylaldehyde ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{O}_2$) and β -hydroxynaphthaldehyde ($\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2$) show the NH proton signals at δ 5.80, 5.65 and 5.40, respectively

and these disappear completely in the corresponding boron complexes.

In the ligands $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{ONS}$ and $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{ONS}$, the phenolic OH proton resonance signal appears as broad signals at δ 9.25 and 9.9, respectively and which disappear in the 1:1 boron complexes. Thus, its deprotonation supports the coordination of phenolic oxygen to boron. However, in 1:2 complexes, these peaks are observed in the form of hydrogen bonded OH protons indicating the non-involvement of phenolic proton in the complex formation. A downfield shift in the resonance signal of alkyl and aryl protons is also observed and this is due to the deshielding of protons on account of the coordination of azomethine nitrogen to the boron atom.

The ^{11}B nmr chemical shift (δ 8.80) of the 1:2 derivatives shows the tetracoordinated state of boron.

The sulphonamides have long been known to possess significant biocidal activity and the Schiff bases derived from them are also expected to inherit these characteristics. These can be structurally represented as follows,

These Schiff bases react with boron isopropoxide in 1:1 and 1:2 molar ratios as indicated below¹⁹,

where, HO-N-NH = donor system of the sulphonamide Schiff base.

The resulting boron Schiff base derivatives can be structurally represented as

The ^{11}B nmr signals appear at δ 2.83 and 2.06 corresponding to the tetracoordinated state of boron in these derivatives.

Synthesis of boron derivatives involving aryloxyboranes :

Aryloxyboranes differ markedly from their alkoxy counterparts due to the greater $-M$ effect of the phenyl ring and thereby behave as stronger Lewis acids. As a consequence of this, a number of adducts with nitrogen donor ligands are formed^{20,21}. Thus, with the Schiff bases, the triphenoxyborane forms 1 : 1 adducts only.

Synthesis of boron derivatives involving B-O-B bonding :

A new series of boron complexes having B-O-B linkage can be obtained by the reactions of oxybis-(diacetoxyborane) with a variety of Schiff bases. The reaction product of boric oxide with acetic anhydride was identified as triacetoxyborane by Pictet and Geleznoff²². Dimroth²³ repeated its preparation and found the ratio of acetic acid to boric acid as 2 : 1. He, therefore, concluded that the product was oxybis(diacetoxyborane) and not the triacetoxyborane. The oxybis(diacetoxyborane) structure was subsequently established by Hayter²⁴ on the basis of molecular weight and X-ray diffraction measurements.

The structure of oxybis(diacetoxyborane) has now been very well supported by ^{11}B nmr and IR spectral studies^{25,26}. Taking into account the inductive effect, ^{11}B resonance signal should appear at a slightly lower field in the spectrum of oxybis-(diacetoxyborane) than the boron signal in the spectra of alkoxy and aryloxyboranes (δ -14 to -19). It is not, however, so and the chemical shift for the boron signal in this compound is observed at δ 1.1 \pm 1.0. This is rather due to the shielding

of the boron atom through chelation by one of the acetoxy carbonyls.

The oxybis(diacetoxyborane) undergoes facile reactions with different types of Schiff bases to produce a variety of simple or mixed type of derivatives²⁷⁻³¹.

Mixed derivatives :

^{11}B nmr spectra of 1 : 1 benzothiazoline derivatives show two sharp peaks at δ 18.4 and 2.8 confirming the existence of boron atoms in tri- and tetracoordinated states, respectively, whereas 2 : 1 products give only one signal at δ 2.06 suggesting the tetracoordinated state of both the boron atoms.

Synthesis of boron derivatives of unsymmetrical boranes :

A variety of Schiff base and allied derivatives of unsymmetrical boranes can be prepared by the reactions of 2-isopropoxybenzo-1,3-dioxo-2-borole with azomethines as well as Schiff base derived from azines, semi- and thiosemi-carbazones and *S* methyl and *S*-benzylthiocarbazates³². These reactions are quite facile in the medium of dry benzene as shown below,

TABLE 1—¹³C NMR DATA OF LIGAND AND ITS BORON COMPLEX
Chemical shift in δ (ppm)

Structure	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	150.92	115.30	128.91	119.03	126.58	116.94	115.67	12.61	178.91			
 (In CDCl ₃)	150.8	115.6	130.5	118.7	128.2	117.2	115.71	14.5	180.2	150.8	107.5	119.1

where, $\widehat{\text{NXH}}$ and $\widehat{\text{HONXH}}$ = donor systems of Schiff bases; X = O or S.

The resulting complexes are coloured solids with sharp melting points and are monomeric in nature. ¹¹B nmr spectral studies indicate the presence of tricoordinated boron in the 1:1 derivatives and tri- as well as tetracoordinated states in the 2:1 derivatives²⁸.

where, X=O or S; Y=NH₂, SCH₃ or SCH₂C₆H₅.

The negligible shifting of azomethine carbon signal (marked by 7) in ¹³C nmr spectra (Table 1) of the complex [OC₆H₄OB](HO.C₆H₄C(CH₃)₂):NNC:SNH₂] as compared to the ligand clearly substantiates the fact that azomethine moiety is not involved in coordination. However, a shift in the carbon signal (marked by 9) attached with sulphur indicates the involvement of sulphur atom in complexation with boron atom.

Similar reactions of 2-isopropoxybenzo-1,3-dioxo-2-borole with salicylaldehyde sulphathiazoles²⁴ result in the isolation of the following derivatives,

Further, to confirm the molecular association of these derivatives, the mass spectrum (Chart 1) of one representative compound, viz. *o*-hydroxyacetophenone azinoboron complex was recorded. The molecular ion peak is observed at *m/e* 386, which corresponds to their monomeric nature.

Organoboranes containing sulphur play an important role in the synthetic organic chemistry. These find uses as synthetic intermediates due to their ready availability and ease of reactivity and are thus unique among organometallic reagents. The unsymmetrical borane derivatives containing sulphur can be prepared by the reactions of 2-isopropoxy-1,3-dithia-2-borole with monofunctional bidentate Schiff bases in 1:1 and bifunctional tridentate Schiff bases²⁵ in 1:1 and 2:1 molar ratios as

Similar reactions with the Schiff bases derived from azines^{8,9} yield the following type of derivatives,

2-Isopropoxybenzo-1,3-thiaza-2-borole also undergoes facile reactions with bifunctional tridentate benzothiazolines in 1:1 and 2:1 molar ratios and the structures of the resulting products can be indicated as

Synthesis of boron derivatives of phenyl(dihydroxy)borane :

Another series of organoboron derivatives of Schiff bases can be obtained by the reactions of phenyl(dihydroxy)borane with different types of azomethines^{8,7}. These reactions are carried out in presence of benzene over a Stark's assembly and the water liberated is collected azeotropically with benzene.

where, X = O or S ; R = CH₂CH₃, C₆H₄, N = C.NH₂, N = CSCH₃ and N = CSCH₂C₆H₅; n = 1, 2 or 3.

Synthesis of boron derivatives involving B-F bonding :

Boron trifluoride diacetic acid (BF₃.2AcOH) or boron trifluoride etherate (BF₃.Et₂O) also undergoes reactions with different types of Schiff bases^{8,8,9}. However, replacement of fluorine is not so facile. The boron trifluoride diacetic acid reacts with *N*-alkyl or aryl salicylaldimines as follows,

Schiff bases having the phenolic group are capable of replacing the fluorine, whereas those having an alcoholic group, such as *N*-(2-hydroxypropyl) benzaldimine, do not undergo such a replacement reaction.

In the resulting derivatives, further replacement of fluorine is not possible even under drastic conditions due to the stable tetracoordinated state of boron. These are generally high melting coloured solids and are very much resistant to hydrolysis. Boron trifluoride etherate also undergoes similar reactions. The replacement of the fluorine atom from the BF₃ molecule possibly takes place by the SN² type of reaction mechanism.

Chart 1—Mass spectrum of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone azinato-boron complex.

where, R = alkyl or aryl group.

The reactions of $\text{BF}_3 \cdot 2\text{AcOH}$ with Schiff bases derived from azines and semi- or thiosemi-carbazones can be depicted by the following equations,

where, X = O, S.

In ^{19}F nmr spectra, only a singlet is observed at δ 28 in the case of semicarbazone and δ 23 in the case of thiosemicarbazone derivatives, and this shows the presence of only a single fluorine atom in the resulting complexes.

Synthesis of boron derivatives involving M-O-M' type of bonding :

A number of papers and patents^{40,41} appear in the literature on the use of metalboraxones, stannoboranes as well as compounds having Sn-O-M type of linkage as plastic stabilisers, bactericides, fungicides, lubricants and water repellents. The possibility of synthesising inorganic polymers with heterometalloxane backbone structure has further stimulated interest in the synthesis of such binuclear derivatives.

The equimolar reactions of phenylboronic acid with boron or aluminium isopropoxide yield the following type of derivatives,

where, M = B or Al.

The resulting monoisopropoxy derivatives further react with ligands having a phenolic group,

such as Schiff bases, azines, semi- or thiosemi-carbazones or S-benzylthiocarbazates so as to produce the desired products.

These complexes are coloured solids with high m.ps. and in the ^{11}B nmr spectrum, a sharp peak at δ 23.20 suggests the tricoordinated state for the boron atom.

For the synthesis of derivatives having B-O-Sn type of bonding, phenylboronic acid is first of all allowed to react with monofunctional bidentate Schiff base in equimolar ratio.

The resulting derivative then undergoes reaction with dibutyltin oxide in 2 : 1 molar ratio to yield B-O-Sn type of derivatives.

The ^{11}B nmr signal appears at δ 2.2 suggesting the tetracoordinated state for both the boron atoms.

Equimolar reactions of diphenylsilanediol with oxybis(diacetoxyborane) and bifunctional tridentate Schiff base result in the synthesis of the following type of derivatives,

where, HONXH = bifunctional tridentate Schiff base molecule.

The ^{11}B nmr spectra give two peaks at δ 20.5 and 1.4 suggesting the tri- and tetra-coordinated states for the boron atoms in the resulting complexes.

Similarly, the reaction of 2-isopropoxybenzo-1,3-dioxo-2-borole with phenylboronic acid or oxybisdiacetoxy borane yields B-O-B type of binuclear derivatives.

Biological studies .

The application of boron compounds in the cancer therapy^{4,5} has revoked considerable interest due to the unique nuclear property of non-radioactive isotope to absorb thermal neutrons ¹⁰B which has an exceptionally large cross section capture area. Alkylboronic acids have been shown to act as reversible enzyme inhibitors and the extent of inhibition depends on the alkyl chain length^{4,5}. The uses of organoboranes as insecticides, fungicides, plant growth agents^{4,4}, soil conditioners, herbicides and weed killers have also been described.

A few representative boron Schiff base complexes have been screened for their activity on pathogenic gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria^{4,5}. The results show that the organoboron complexes of Schiff bases derived from *S*-benzyl dithiocarbazates, sulpha drugs and semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones inhibit the growth of gram-positive as well as gram-negative bacteria even at very low concentrations. It has also been shown that the complexation increases the activity as the boron complexes are much more active than the ligands themselves. In general, the complexes derived from thio-Schiff bases or those containing sulphur show greater activity than those, which do not have it. The fungicidal activity of boron thiosemicarbazone complexes is appreciably higher than the two well known fungicides, Bevistin and PCNB, which have been reported to be quite active against phytopathogens.

Acknowledgement

The author sincerely thanks his present as well as earlier coworkers, Drs. R. V. Singh, H. B. Singh, S. R. M. Tripathi, P. K. Singh, (Miss) L. Bahl and K. K. Chaturvedi for carrying out the experimental

work. Financial support from C.S.I.R. and U.G.C., New Delhi, is also gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. M. MINAMI and A. KITAMURE, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1974, 80, 133012.
2. P. H. R. B. LEMON, *Br. Plastics*, 1963, 36, 336 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1965, 63, 11786).
3. H. NAKAMURA, Y. IITAKA, T. KITACHARA, T. OKAZAKI and Y. OKAMI, *J. Antibiot*, 1977, 30, 714.
4. M. GRASSBERGER, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1979, 91, 39316.
5. Y. OKA and I. YANAGISAWA, *Nucl. Technol.*, 1981, 55, 642
6. A. H. SOLOWAY, R. L. WRIGHT and J. R. MESSER, *J. Pharmacol. Exp Ther*, 1961, 134, 177 (*Chem Abstr.*, 1962, 56, 872).
7. H. A. CYBA, U. S. PAT, 3 398 170/1968 (*Chem. Abstr*, 1968, 69, 6363).
8. T. SNAMI and S. UMEZAVA, *Bull Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1956, 29, 975.
9. H. THEISS, H. SCHOEMBERGER and K. BORAH, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1966, 299, 1031.
10. J. P. TANDON and H. B. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, 17, 620; 1979, 18, 529.
11. J. P. TANDON and H. B. SINGH, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1977, 7, 547; 1978, 8, 265, *Acta Chim. (Budapest)*, 1978, 98, 81.
12. J. P. TANDON and P. K. SINGH, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, 43, 1755.
13. J. P. TANDON and P. K. SINGH, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1984, 93, 53.
14. H. JADAMUS, Q. FERNANDO and H. FREISER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 86, 3056.
15. R. G. CHARLES and H. FREISER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, 18, 422.
16. L. F. LINDOY and S. E. LIVINGSTONE, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1967, 1, 365.
17. C. C. LEE, A. SHAMA and L. J. THERIOT, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, 10, 1669.
18. J. P. TANDON, K. K. CHATURVEDI and R. V. SINGH, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1984, 14, 1085; *J. Prakt. Chem*, 1984, 326, 817.
19. J. P. TANDON, K. K. CHATURVEDI and R. V. SINGH, *J. Prakt. Chem*, 1985, 325, 144.
20. T. COLELOUGH, W. GERRARD and M. F. LAPPERT, *J. Chem. Soc*, 1956, 3006.
21. H. BEYER and H. NOTH, *Chem. Ber*, 1960, 93, 1078.
22. A. PICTET and A. GLEZENEFF, *Chem. Ber*, 1903, 36, 2269
23. O. DIMROTH, R. RUCHTI, R. SAGSTETTER, J. HETZER, H. BERNZOTT, C. BAMBERGER, O. REHMANN and R. SCHWEIZER, *Justus Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1925, 446, 97 (*Chem Abstr*, 1926, 20, 1052).
24. R. G. HATER, A. W. LAIBENGAYER and P. G. THOMPSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 4243.
25. J. P. ONAK, H. LANDESMAN, R. E. WILLIAMS and I. SHAPIARO, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, 63, 1533.
26. L. A. DUNCENSON, W. GERRARD, M. F. LAPPERT, H. PYAZORA and H. SHAFERMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3652.
27. J. P. TANDON, S. M. TRIPATHI and R. V. SINGH, *J. Chin. Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 27, 51.
28. J. P. TANDON, K. K. CHATURVEDI and R. V. SINGH, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1983, 12, 155.

TANDON : SYNTHESIS OF SOME NOVEL BORON-SCHIFF BASE AND ALLIED DERIVATIVES

29. J. P. TANDON and H. B. SINGH, *Synth. React Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1985, 15, 391.
30. J. P. TANDON and H. B. SINGH, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1980, 42, 793.
31. J. P. TANDON, P. K. SINGH and H. B. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, 20, 202.
32. J. P. TANDON, R. V. SINGH and L. BAHL, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1984, 115, 251; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, 22, 951.
33. J. P. TANDON and L. BAHL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, 25, 54.
34. J. P. TANDON, L. BAHL and R. V. SINGH, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1984, 14, 1135.
35. J. P. TANDON, R. V. SINGH and L. BAHL, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1983, 13, 613.
36. J. P. TANDON, R. V. SINGH and L. BAHL, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1985, in the press.
37. J. P. TANDON and S. R. M. TRIPATHI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, 17, 618.
38. J. P. TANDON and P. K. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, 21, 833.
39. J. P. TANDON and S. R. M. TRIPATHI, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1978, 4, 917.
40. G. WEISSENBERGER, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1967, 67, 1068.
41. J. ELLERMANN, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1979, 34, 975.
42. G. I. LOCHES, *Am. J. Roentgenol.*, 1936, 36, 1.
43. V. K. ANTONOV, T. V. IVANINA, I. V. BEREZIN and K. MARTINEX, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk SSSR*, 1968, 183, 1435.
44. R. A. WILDES and T. F. NEABS, *J. Exp. Bot.*, 1969, 20, 591.
45. J. P. TANDON, L. BAHL and S. K. SINHA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1984, 53, 566.